

NOTES

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Aurantiamide Acetate from *Artocarpus integrefolia* Linn.

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Manuscript received 21 April 1980, accepted 5 November 1980

IN course of our investigation on some Indian medicinal plants, we were interested to examine the seeds of *Artocarpus integrefolia* Linn. which has been found to elaborate a number of flavones, steroids and triterpenes. Here we report the isolation of a dipeptide which has been identified as Aurantiamide acetate(I), the first known dipeptide of the plant origin, previously isolated from the seeds of *Piper aurantiacum* Wall¹.

The petroleum-ether extract of the dried seeds of *Artocarpus integrefolia* Linn. (pretreated with acetone in cold) furnished colourless silky needles on keeping in cold. The compound $C_{27}H_{28}N_2O_4$, M^+ 444, m.p. 188-89°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 30.65$ ($CHCl_3$) was neutral in character (yield 0.0004%).

The IR spectrum showed the characteristic band for acetoxy function at ν_{max} (KBr) 1720, 1249 and 1042 cm^{-1} , NH function at 3330 cm^{-1} , amido carbonyl at 1652 cm^{-1} , aromatic system at 1620, 1515 and 1484 cm^{-1} and mono-substituted phenyl nucleus at 740 and 690 cm^{-1} .

The UV absorption spectrum showed λ_{max} 213 and 230 nm with log ϵ values 3.37 and 3.19 respectively, suggesting the presence of aromatic system in the compound.

The PMR spectrum (90 MHz, $CdCl_2$, TMS) showed the presence of aromatic, amido, benzylic, methine and acetate protons in it. The δ -values are

7.53-7.90 (m, 5H, a), 7.4 (sh. s, 5H, b), 7.21 (br. s, 5H, b'), 6.9 (br. d, J=9.0 Hz, 1H, c), 6.2 (br. d, J=8.5 Hz, 1H, c'), 4.86 (m, 1H, d), 4.26-4.41 (m, 1H, d'), 3.95 & 3.83 (dd, J=6 & 3Hz, 2H, e' & e''), 3.20 & 3.10 (dd, J=8.5 & 9.5 Hz, 2H, e''' & e'''), 2.73 (d, J=7Hz, 2H, f), 1.98 (s, 3H, g).

The Mass Spectrum of the compound showed the loss of 60, 77, 91, 105 etc. units supporting the presence of acetoxy, phenyl, benzyl and benzoyl groups respectively. Other significant peaks also are in consistent with the structure(I).

The physical data are suggestive that it is a dipeptide identical to Aurantiamide acetate. This is the second-time isolation of the dipeptide from plant origin. The direct comparison with authentic specimen was not possible for paucity of material of the previous workers.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their respectful thanks to Dr. S. C. Bhattacharyya, Director and Prof. A. Sen, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute for their interest in the work. One of us (A.K.M.) thanks the I.C.A.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Research Fellowship.

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Chemical Examination of Essential Oil of *Coleus aromaticus* Benth

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*Manuscript received 31 March 1980, revised 1 August 1980,
accepted 29 October 1980*

PLANT : *Coleus aromaticus* Benth (Family-Labiatae)
Isolation Procedure : Steam Distillation (Yield-0.04-0.05%), *Physical Constants* : Sp. gravity 0.9254, n_D^{20} 1.4896, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 8^{\circ}36'$, Acid value 3.276, Ester value 6.1314, Ester value after acetylation 152.576 and carbonyl value as $C_{10}H_{16}O$ -2.58%.

Previous Work : Few workers^{1,2} have reported the chemistry of essential oil obtained from leaves and separated phenolic and non-phenolic terpenes of the oil.

The completely characterised constituents of the oil are listed in Table 1.

TABLE—1

Compound	Yield(%)	Methods of identification.
Terpinolene	3.75	IR, Maleic anhydride adduct ² , Co-TLC & GLC
α -pinene	3.20	IR, NMR, Co-TLC & GLC
β -pinene	2.50	NMR, Nopinic acid, Co-TLC & GLC
β -caryophyllene	4.20	IR, NMR, Co-TLC & GLC
Methyl eugenol	2.10	IR, Co-TLC & GLC
Thymol	41.80	IR, Colour reactions, Co-TLC & GLC
1, 8-Cineole	5.45	IR, Iodol addition comp., Co-TLC & GLC
Eugenol	4.40	IR, n_D^{25} (1.5414), Co-TLC & GLC
Carvacrol	13.25	IR, n_D^{25} (1.5234), Phenylurethane, Co-TLC & GLC
β -Phellanderene	1.90	IR, Co-TLC & GLC

All the melting points of derivatives were compared with the melting points given by Gunther³.

Acknowledgement

We are indebted to Prof. H. Wagner, Director, Institut für Pharmazeutische Arzneimittellehre, Munchen (W. Germany) for IR, NMR and GLC. Thanks are also due to UGC for sanctioning the research project to one of us (R.K.B.) under which this work could be done.

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Chemical Examination of Essential Oil from the leaves of *Tagetes-erecta* Linn.

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Manuscript received 31 March 1980, revised 1 August 1980, accepted 29 October 1980

PLANT: *Tagetes-erecta* Linn. (Family Compositae).
Procedure—Steam distillation (Yield 0.3%)
Physical Constants—Sp. gravity 0.8936, n_D^{25} 1.6147,

$[\alpha]_D^{25} + 2.436$, Acid value 1.4784, Ester value 30.68, Ester value after acetylation 142.35 and carbonyl value as $C_{10}H_{16}O$ 12.94%. *Previous work*: Few workers^{1,2} have reported the chemistry of essential oil from flowering tops and separated phenolic and non-phenolic terpenes of the oil.

The completely characterised constituents of the oil are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound	Yield(%)	Methods of identification
δ -limonene	19.67	IR, n_D^{25} 1.4746, Co-TLC and GLC
α -pinene	1.36	IR, n_D^{25} 1.4662, Co-TLC and GLC
β -pinene	0.89	IR, Nopinic acid ³ , Co-TLC and GLC
Dipentene	0.67	IR, Co-TLC and GLC
Ocimene	7.61	IR, n_D^{25} 1.4857, Co-TLC and GLC
β -phellandrene	4.97	IR, Co-TLC and GLC
Linalool	26.80	IR, n_D^{25} 1.4624, Co-TLC and GLC
Geraniol	0.86	IR, NMR, Co-TLC and GLC
Menthol	0.93	IR, Co-TLC and GLC
Tagetone	13.39	IR, Methyl-isobutyl Ketone adduct ⁴ , Co-TLC and GLC
Nonanal	1.34	IR, NMR, Co-TLC and GLC
Linalylacetate	3.56	IR, n_D^{25} 1.6327, Co-TLC and GLC

Acknowledgement

We are indebted to Prof. H. Wagner, Director, Institut für Pharmazeutische Arzneimittellehre, Munchen (W. Germany) for IR, NMR and GLC. Thanks are also due to U.G.C. for sanctioning the research project to one of us (R.K.B.) under which this work could be done.

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